

Sensing Resources Reduction for Vehicle Detection with Integrated Sensing and Communications

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Abstract—Integrated Sensing and Communications (ISAC) aims at incorporating radar and communications functionalities into a single system, achieving higher spectral efficiency through their joint operation. This paper proposes a methodology for reducing resource elements and scanning beams used in the target detection stage of ISAC. Building upon the well-known symbol domain Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) ISAC processing algorithm, its relevant characteristics and limits are considered to minimize the periodicity of sensing resource elements. Moreover, a methodology for finding the required beams to sense a scenario using the radar range equation in a link-budget analysis is proposed and later illustrated via simulations. The simulations show that it is possible to cover a road scenario using a limited number of beams and resource elements from a New Radio (NR) OFDM frame.

Index Terms—ISAC, vehicular, resource allocation

I. INTRODUCTION

ISAC is expected to become a fundamental capability of future-generation mobile networks providing the integration of communication and sensing, which have traditionally been developed separately, into a unique multi-functional system. The recent increasing interest from the research community has produced significant literature covering waveform design, resource optimization, and applied information theory. For a comprehensive survey on ISAC, the reader can refer to [1]. Even though ISAC has been identified as a key technology for 6G, there are opportunities for its implementation in 5G infrastructure. Key 5G technologies such as massive MIMO and the usage of mmWave could enable the development of feasible solutions without significant changes to the currently used infrastructure. ISAC in a 5G ecosystem has already been explored in [2], [3], primarily based on the processing algorithm proposed in [4], proving the feasibility of OFDM, and hence, the 5G waveform for sensing.

One of the applications of ISAC that has received more attention is its usage for Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) [5]. ISAC for vehicular applications could eventually become an enabler for use cases such as autonomous driving and vehicle platooning. However, infrastructure-based sensing, which could also be applied to ITS, has been studied more extensively due to the higher availability of resources and signal-

processing capacity. For example, multi-beam approaches have been proposed in which a Base Station (BS) allocates one beam for communications and the other for sensing [3], [6]. In this setup, the sensing beam must scan the entire scenario to detect targets and estimate their parameters. The total available power needs to be split between the two functionalities. Hence, reducing the resources needed for sensing would enable more power for communications, enhancing its performance.

In existing work, the evaluation of the performance of the sensing function is usually done in terms of the accuracy of the estimation of the targets' parameters. For a comprehensive review of the metrics and fundamental limits typically considered by authors, the reader can refer to [7]. Moreover, the beams transmitted for sensing are planned following strategies such as considering the 3 dB angular width of the array pattern [3], or by rotating the sensing beam an arbitrary number of degrees [6]. This paper considers an alternative approach by considering the ability of the system to detect vehicular targets as the performance metric and applying a link-budget analysis using the radar's range equation to minimise the number of beams required to sense a scenario. Moreover, regarding resource elements of the transmitted OFDM grid, authors typically consider using the full payload for sensing. However, we analyze the limits of the ISAC algorithm to subsample the OFDM grid for sensing without compromising the sensing functionality.

The paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the system model and the OFDM processing algorithm used for ISAC, the relevant aspects of this algorithm for the explored application, and introduces the target detection aspects. Section III explores the possibilities for resource reduction and the limits in terms of resource separation for the correct functioning of the ISAC algorithm, including a methodology for planning the beams required for sensing the scenario. Finally, Section IV presents the simulation results with examples of the application of the proposed algorithm, as well as the evaluation of the detection performance with different resource usage levels. The conclusions of the paper are given in Section V.

Throughout this paper, the following notation conventions are used: capital bold letters represent matrices while lower-

case bold letters represent vectors, $(\cdot)^*$ represents the conjugate transpose, and $\|\cdot\|_p$ represents the p -norm operator.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND ISAC RADAR PROCESSING

A. System Model

We assume a Base Station (BS) equipped with a phased array, that communicates with users and simultaneously senses the environment in a mono-static setup using the 5G-NR OFDM waveform. To do so, the transmitter sends at the same time a communication and a sensing stream, defined by:

$$\mathbf{s}_t = \sqrt{\frac{P_t}{N_t}} (\sqrt{(1-\rho)} \mathbf{w}_c \mathbf{x}_c + \sqrt{\rho} \mathbf{w}_s \mathbf{x}_s), \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{s}_t , \mathbf{x}_c , \mathbf{x}_s are the transmitted signal, and the modulated data for the communications and the sensing streams, respectively, in the time domain; P_t , N_t are the transmit power and the number of transmit antennas; \mathbf{w}_c , \mathbf{w}_s are the precoding vectors of shape $N_t \times 1$ for the communication and the sensing stream, and $0 \leq \rho \leq 1$ is a scaling factor that controls the power balance between communications and sensing. Both \mathbf{x}_c , \mathbf{x}_s are considered to have normalized power.

We also assume that the BS is capable of in-band full-duplex, so it can act as a sensing receiver while transmitting the signal described by (1), and do not consider the influence of self-interference. For the purposes of this paper, the interference of the communication stream on the sensing receiver will be neglected, and more in-depth analysis will be reserved for future work. Strategies that reduce the impact of the communication data on the sensing include projecting the communication signal into the null space of the sensing direction and manipulating the receiving beamformer to introduce a null in the direction of the communications user. For clarity, we define the sensing part of the transmitted signal as:

$$\mathbf{s} = \sqrt{\rho \frac{P_t}{N_t}} \mathbf{w}_s \mathbf{x}_s. \quad (2)$$

Considering the point scatterer model with L targets and that at the receiver the signals from the $N_r = N_t$ receiving antennas are combined using \mathbf{w}_s^* , we have the following transmit/receive relationship:

$$\mathbf{r}[t] = \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} h_l \mathbf{w}_s^* \mathbf{v}_l \mathbf{v}_l^* \mathbf{s}[t - \tau_l] e^{j2\pi f_{D,l} t} e^{j\varphi_l} + \mathbf{z}[t], \quad (3)$$

where h_l , τ_l , $f_{D,l}$, φ_l are the attenuation, delay, Doppler shift, and random phase shift experienced by the signal scattered from the l -th target, and \mathbf{z} represents the received noise, considered as zero-mean circularly symmetric white Gaussian. Lastly, \mathbf{v}_l represents the array response towards the direction of the l -th target, which for a Uniform Rectangular Array (URA) located in the $y-z$ plane is given by:

$$\mathbf{v}_l = [e^{j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} (\mathbf{y} \sin \theta_l \cos \varphi_l + \mathbf{z} \sin \varphi_l)}], \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{y} , \mathbf{z} are the vectors containing the positions of each element of the array in the y and z axis, respectively, and

θ_l , φ_l are the azimuth and elevation angles in the direction of the l -th target.

The attenuation h_l in (3) is given by:

$$h_l = \sqrt{\frac{c_0^2 \sigma_{\text{RCS},l}}{(4\pi)^3 d_l^4 f_c^2}}, \quad (5)$$

where c_0 , $\sigma_{\text{RCS},l}$, d_l and f_c represent the speed of light, the radar cross-section of the l -th reflecting object, its distance to the transceiver, and the carrier frequency, respectively. The relevant parameters for sensing from (3) are the delay τ_l and Doppler shift $f_{D,l}$, from which the target's distance and relative velocity can be obtained.

The received power of the l -th scatterer P_{r_l} can be expressed in terms of ρ , P_t , h_l , and the achieved array gain for transmission and reception, which will be considered equal $G_{T_x} = G_{R_x} = G$ and can be obtained for the l -th scatterer as:

$$G_l = \frac{\mathbf{w}_s^* \mathbf{v}_l \mathbf{v}_l^* \mathbf{w}_s}{\mathbf{w}_s^* \mathbf{w}_s}. \quad (6)$$

Then P_{r_l} is given by:

$$P_{r_l} = \rho P_t G_l^2 h_l^2. \quad (7)$$

B. OFDM Radar processing for ISAC

The selected method for processing the echoes is presented in [4] and used extensively in the literature [2], [3], [8]. The transmitted sensing signal \mathbf{s} can be expressed in terms of the OFDM resource grid, which we will denote by the matrix \mathbf{F}_{T_x} , where the $i = 0, \dots, N-1$ rows represent subcarriers and the $k = 0, \dots, M-1$ columns represent OFDM symbols. In (2), \mathbf{x}_s is obtained by performing OFDM modulation of \mathbf{F}_{T_x} . At the sensing receiver, we have \mathbf{F}_{R_x} whose element (i, k) is given by:

$$\mathbf{F}_{R_x(i,k)} = \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} h_l \mathbf{F}_{T_x(i,k)} e^{j2\pi T_0 f_{D,l} k} e^{-j2\pi \tau_l (i \Delta f + f_0)} e^{j\varphi_l} + \mathbf{Z}_{(i,k)}, \quad (8)$$

where the new terms T_0 , Δf , and f_0 represent the OFDM symbol duration, subcarrier spacing (SCS), and the frequency of the lowest frequency subcarrier, respectively. In addition, $\mathbf{Z}_{(i,k)}$ represents the (i, k) element of the receiver's noise matrix. The modulated data of the transmitted grid can be removed by element-wise division, leaving:

$$\mathbf{F} = \frac{\mathbf{F}_{R_x}}{\mathbf{F}_{T_x}}. \quad (9)$$

Similar to communications, the orthogonality between resource elements at the OFDM sensing receiver needs to be maintained. For this, it is required for the cyclic-prefix (CP) duration T_{CP} to be larger than the roundtrip propagation time to the furthest target $T_{\text{CP}} > \tau_{\text{max}} = \frac{2d_{\text{max}}}{c_0}$, where d_{max} is the distance to that target. Moreover, the SCS Δf needs to be an order of magnitude larger than the largest occurring Doppler shift $f_{D_{\text{max}}}$. A rule of thumb typically

applied is $\Delta f > 10f_{D_{\max}} = (20v_{\max}f_c)/c_0$, with v_{\max} being the maximum velocity of targets relative to the transceiver. In terms of the NR waveform parameters, these constraints limit the maximum sensing distance and the maximum target velocity, as shown in the examples in Table I, where normal CP duration has been considered for each numerology.

TABLE I: Maximum sensing distance and velocity

System Configuration		Sensing Limits	
SCS (kHz)	f_c (GHz)	d_{\max} (m)	v_{\max} (km/h)
15	3.5	704	231
30	5	344	324
120	24	88	270

The process of estimating the parameters τ_l and f_{D_l} is a frequency estimation problem, and a useful tool for this problem is the periodogram. To process the matrix \mathbf{F} , a 2D-periodogram can be obtained by [9]:

$$P_{\mathbf{F}}(n, m) = \frac{1}{NM} \left| \sum_{i=0}^{N_p-1} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{M_p-1} \mathbf{F} e^{-j2\pi \frac{km}{M_p}} \right) e^{j2\pi \frac{in}{N_p}} \right|^2, \quad (10)$$

where N_p , and M_p represent the rows and columns of the periodogram respectively, which can be different from the number of subcarriers N and OFDM symbols M if, for example, zero padding is used to obtain a power of two number of FFT points.

Given a target present in the scenario with parameters mapped to the bins (n_0, m_0) of the periodogram defined in (10), the height of the peak produced by the target is given by:

$$P_{\mathbf{F}}(n_0, m_0) \leq NMP_{r_0}, \quad (11)$$

where P_{r_0} is given by (7). The equality is reached when the location of the bin is exactly that of the target parameters.

C. Target detection

Two fundamental concepts related to target detection are resolution and Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR). The resolution defines the ability of the sensing system to distinguish targets from each other and static clutter. The SNR affects the probability of correct target detection in noisy signals.

Starting with the resolution, from classical radar theory, the range ΔR and Doppler Δf_D resolutions are related to the sensing bandwidth and time, respectively. In terms of OFDM parameters, they can be expressed as:

$$\Delta R = \frac{c_0}{2N\Delta f}, \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta f_D = \frac{1}{MT_0}. \quad (13)$$

Then for the detection of the l -th target in terms of resolution, we need

$$\min_i |d_{T_x-l} - d_{T_x-i}| \geq \Delta R, \quad (14)$$

$$\min_i |f_{D,l} - f_{D,i}| \geq \Delta f_D, \quad (15)$$

with $i = 0, \dots, l-1, l+1, \dots, L-1$ and $d_{T_x-l}, d_{T_x-i}, f_{D,l}, f_{D,i}$ represent the distance between the transceiver and targets l and i , as well as Doppler shift caused by targets l and i .

Turning to the SNR, given that the noise considered is zero-mean circularly symmetric white Gaussian, the statistics of the noise in the beams of the periodogram given by (10) follow a Gamma distribution $\Gamma(1, \sigma_n^2)$ [9], where σ_n^2 is the noise power. Following a constant false alarm rate (CFAR) algorithm for the target detection, it can be found that the decision threshold η_P for a given probability of false alarm p_{FA} is given by [9]:

$$\eta_P = -\sigma_n^2 \ln(1 - (1 - p_{\text{FA}})^{\frac{1}{N_p M_p}}). \quad (16)$$

The decision of whether a target is present at a periodogram bin is given by:

$$P_{\mathbf{F}}(n, m) \underset{H_1}{\overset{H_0}{\leq}} \eta_P. \quad (17)$$

In (17), H_0 represents the null hypothesis, and H_1 is the hypothesis for a present target. Combining (17) with (11) we get that for target detection we need:

$$NMP_{r_l} > \eta_P. \quad (18)$$

III. REDUCTION OF SENSING RESOURCES

So far, the analysis assumes that the whole OFDM resource grid is used for sensing. In (8) this translates to sampling every subcarrier and symbol, setting the sampling period along rows as T_0 and columns as Δf . However, it might be desirable not to use all available resources for sensing if possible, hence being able to allocate more resources to the communication functionality. Two ways of sensing resource reduction will be considered: subsampling the OFDM grid by using the limits presented in Table I, and minimizing the number of scanning beams by using a link-budget analysis.

Starting with the grid subsampling, the required periodicity for sensing resources must guarantee that no aliasing occurs when obtaining the periodogram in (10). Applying the sampling theorem and the limits presented in Table I, we can obtain the maximum required separation in subcarriers, which we will denote as $\Delta f_{s_{\max}}$, given by:

$$\Delta f_{s_{\max}} = \frac{c_0}{2d_{\max}\Delta f}, \quad (19)$$

while, similarly assuming a maximum allowable Doppler shift of $0.1\Delta f$, the maximum separation in symbols $\Delta T_{s_{\max}}$ is 5 OFDM symbols for all values of SCS.

With the appropriate Δf_s and ΔT_s , as long as resources are distributed across the entire bandwidth and time, there is no loss in resolution. The main impact of such resource usage is the degradation in the periodogram's SNR given by the lower N and M , decreasing the periodogram's processing gain. We will denote the number of subcarriers and OFDM symbols

used for the sensing as N_s, M_s , respectively. Checking if the selected periodicity is valid is equivalent to evaluating (18) for the worst case location of the sensing scenario, where $d_l = d_{\max}$ and considering a minimum value for the RCS $\sigma_{\text{RCS},\min}$:

$$N_s M_s \rho P_t G^2 \frac{c_0^2 \sigma_{\text{RCS},\min}}{(4\pi)^3 d_{\max}^4 f_c^2} > \eta_P. \quad (20)$$

With a symbol usage factor of $\mu = \frac{1}{\Delta T_{s,\max}}$ and the power scaling factor ρ , the spectral efficiency of the communication channel in (1) can be written as:

$$R/B = ((1 - \mu) \log_2(1 + \text{SNR}) + \mu \log_2(1 + (1 - \rho)\text{SNR})), \quad (21)$$

where R , B , SNR are the communication rate, system bandwidth and SNR at the receiver.

On the other hand, for planning the sensing beams, we want to obtain the least amount of beams that will allow us to sense the environment while fulfilling (18) for all the locations of the sensing scenario. If we divide the scenario in a two-dimensional grid, we can obtain the required beamforming gain at location (x, y) , $\mathbf{G}_{\min}(x, y)$, $x \in \{0, \dots, x_{\max}\}$, $y \in \{0, \dots, y_{\max}\}$, at a distance d_{xy} from the ISAC transceiver, by using again (18):

$$\mathbf{G}_{\min}(x, y) = \eta_P \frac{(4\pi)^3 d_{xy}^4 f_c^2}{N_s M_s \rho P_t c_0^2 \sigma_{\text{RCS},\min}}. \quad (22)$$

For simplicity, we flatten $\mathbf{G}_{\min}(x, y)$ to a $1 \times N_g$ vector \mathbf{g}_{\min} , where N_g is the number of locations in the scenario. Similarly, we denote $\mathbf{W} = [\mathbf{w}_0, \dots, \mathbf{w}_{N_g-1}]$ as the $N_t \times N_g$ matrix with the beamforming vectors \mathbf{w}_i to all locations of the scenario grid, such that \mathbf{w}_i gives the beamforming vector towards the location with \mathbf{w}_{\min_i} gain requirement. We can obtain the array gain matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}$ with dimensions $N_g \times N_g$ by:

$$\hat{\mathbf{W}} = \frac{1}{N_t} (\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{W}) \odot (\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{W}), \quad (23)$$

where \odot denotes the Hadamard product. The element (i, j) of $\hat{\mathbf{W}}$ corresponds to the gain of beam j on the location i of \mathbf{w}_{\min} . By setting $\tilde{\mathbf{W}} = [\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_0, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{N_g-1}]$, we can obtain the matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{W}} = [\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_0, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{N_g-1}]$ by doing element-wise comparison between each column of $\hat{\mathbf{W}}$ with \mathbf{g}_{\min} , and setting 1 if the element is greater, and 0 otherwise. With these results, we can pose the search for the minimum amount of beams that would cover the sensing scenario as an optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{\mathbf{x}} \|\mathbf{x}\|_1, \\ \text{s.t. } & x_0 \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_0 + \dots + x_{N_g-1} \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{N_g-1} \succeq [\mathbf{1}] \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

where $\mathbf{x} \in \{0, 1\}^{N_g}$, $\|\mathbf{x}\|_1$ denotes the 1-norm, \succeq represents an element-wise comparison, and $[\mathbf{1}]$ is a column vector with all elements equal to 1 and dimensioned accordingly. It can be seen that the desired optimization is non-convex but a valid solution can be found via a search method proposed in Algorithm 1, where the process of searching a beam that covers the largest consecutive set of the scenario is described. At the end of the execution of Algorithm 1, we obtain the

found beam \mathbf{b}_n and the remaining subset of the scenario not covered by it with sufficient gain $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_n$. Hence, the process must be repeated until the return subset of the scenario is empty. Convergence is ensured since in (20) it was guaranteed that at least the dedicated beam to a scenario location will provide enough beamforming gain. An analysis of the algorithm reveals that the complexity is on the order of $N_t N_g^2$. Even though the solution scales quadratically with the number of scenario points, this process would not need to be performed constantly, but rather at the initial configuration of the ISAC capable transceiver after its installation.

Data: $\tilde{\mathbf{W}} \in \{0, 1\}^{N_g \times N_g}$, $\mathbf{W} = [\mathbf{w}_0, \dots, \mathbf{w}_{N_g-1}]$

Result: $\mathbf{b}_n, \tilde{\mathbf{W}}_n$

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i ← 0 ;                               /* First location */
k ← 0 ;                               /* First beam */
while  $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_{0:i+1,k} == [\mathbf{1}]$  do
    | i ← i + 1 ; /* Move to next location */
    | k ← k + 1 ; /* Move to next beam */
end
 $\mathbf{b}_n \leftarrow \mathbf{w}_i$  ;                 /* Beam found */
while  $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_{i+1,k} == 1$  do
    | i ← i + 1 ; /* Find all consecutive
    | locations covered by beam */
end
 $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_n = \tilde{\mathbf{W}}_{i+j:N_g, k+1:N_g}$ 

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Algorithm 1: Beam search algorithm

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In order to test the proposed methodology, simulations were conducted for its application for vehicle detection at 5 GHz. The maximum effective isotropic radiated power (EIRP) considered was 43 dBm, and $\rho = 0.5$ was considered according to (1). A scenario consisting of a straight two-way road was considered, with a total of four lanes (2 lanes in each direction) each with a width of 3.5 m, and a length of 300 m. A minimum value of $\sigma_{\text{RCS},\min} = 5$ dBsm was assumed and the p_{FA} was set to 0.01. The maximum sensing time was 10 ms corresponding to a full OFDM frame. For the transmitted waveform an NR-based OFDM with SCS of 30 kHz and bandwidth of 50 MHz transmitted from a 4×4 URA at a height of 30 m, was used.

Maintaining the requirements for sensing resources and assuming a maximum speed of 150 km/h, the distance between subcarriers and symbols was set to 12 and 7, respectively, which would represent one subcarrier for every physical resource block (PRB) and two symbols per slot. Considering. First, it was checked that with this sparse OFDM occupation, it was possible to cover the edge of the scenario, and then the beam planning procedure described in Algorithm 1 was applied. The result is shown in Figure 1, where the BS is considered to be located at the origin of the coordinates.

As shown, two beams were enough to cover the entire scenario. The beam 1 did not provide enough SNR only on 24 bins of a total of 4200 in the scenario, making necessary

Fig. 1: Coverage of beams for the 5 GHz scenario the beam 2. It is worth mentioning that there will be locations where targets are detectable by multiple beams. However, in Figure 1, only the strongest beam is shown for each scenario bin. With the selected parameters, the comparison in spectral efficiency for the communication system using the full OFDM grid for sensing versus the proposed subsampled version is shown in Fig. 2, showing that the solution closely follows the communications-only performance.

Fig. 2: Spectral efficiency comparison

Having tested the capability to fulfil the criteria for target detection in terms of received echo power, we turn our attention to the resolution. To evaluate this, the tool Simulation of Urban Mobility (SUMO) [10] was used to generate the described scenario. The road was populated with vehicles moving at an average speed of 60 km/h, inserted in each direction with a probability of 0.5 every second for one hour. A resource pool was created with different values for sensing time and bandwidth. In each case, the average percentage of time the vehicles were resolved from other cars or static clutter was obtained. The results are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Average percentage resolved time

It can be seen that the detection of vehicles improves considerably with the addition of sensing bandwidth and time. In the case of maximum resource usage, from a total of 2200 vehicles, only 151 were at some point in an undetectable state, for a maximum of 15% of their time in the scenario.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The applicability of ISAC for vehicle detection was shown with satisfactory results. The presented beam planning algorithm showed that the number of beams required to scan a scenario could be reduced. Moreover, the analysis of statistics drawn from the mobility environment simulations shows that most vehicles can be detected even with fewer resources. It was shown that even if at the higher resource usage some vehicles were undetected at some point, this state only accounted for a small percentage of their time present in the sensing scenario. For future work, we plan to study the applicability of ISAC in Multi-User MIMO (MU-MIMO) setting and the optimization of the spectral efficiency for this case.

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